

STRESS WAVES IN THREE LAYERED COMPOSITE AT IMPACT LOADING

V. Polyakov

*Institute of Polymer Mechanics
Latvian University, 23 Aizkraukles, LV-1006, Riga, Latvia*

SUMMARY: The researches on dynamic behavior of composites of layered structural arrangement are carried out as the exact analysis knowledge-based on the wave problem for the conjugate areas of different material is developed. Complexity of the exact analysis considered in the known monographs incompletely receives a replacement by an approximate computation. Herein after the exact solution of wave equation in one-dimensional case (amenably to the spatial coordinate) has been regained through characteristics in order to take a shot at presenting shock waves (or waves of severe discontinuity due to “stick-slip nature” of the first displacement derivatives) in the layered medium. The transverse normal stresses in a three-layer plate of sandwich type were investigated at a short-time dynamic load applied over the entire surface of an upper layer (a planar deformation) and the free back surface of the plate. Analytical procedure for displacements, velocities and stresses caused by the rectangular short-time pulse from a striker, whose duration is not exceeding the double time of a wave travel within the layer was realized. The factors of variation and ramification of a pressure pulse over panel layers involving its transmission and reflection when crossing the contact surfaces of the layers of different kinds in physical properties were deduced. The analysis of stresses was given to compare their magnitudes and for prediction of slabbing failure. In case of symmetric panel structure the stress pattern in the midlayer and on contact surfaces including superposition and branching of pulses was studied.

KEYWORDS: sandwich panel, acoustic impact, plane wave, transverse normal stress, ply separation

INTRODUCTION

The analysis on dynamic behavior of layered composites considered in the known monographs [1,2] gives rise to a different sort of the approximate theories, in which an universal use of the Hamilton action functional leads to dynamic problems of different assumption levels. Actually confining oneself to the framework of one-dimensional problem (amenably to the spatial coordinate), the exact solution of wave equation presenting shock waves in the unbounded elastic medium is in need of complementary validating [2] as compared with dynamically similar model for a longitudinal beam.

The effect of stress waves at slabbing action of a surface layer was experimentally studied in [3] for a number of polymeric materials and in [4] - at impact compression of composites based on carbon fibers and metal matrix. In the former paper the primary emphasis has been done on experimental detection and description for spalling phenomena and cracking dependent on dynamic characteristics of polymers in a range of their sound speed of 1.5-2.5 km/s, specific density 0.9-2.2 g/cm³ by striker's velocity 50-125 m/s. It is significant to note that the stress values under spalling, calculated by the values of a pressure pulse reflected from the free surface of a polymer are essentially by a factor of 1.8-8.4 exceeded the ultimate stress under static tension and the polymer strain therewith exceeds a plastic limit. Temperature exceeding the operating temperature of polymer in conditions of static loads does not reduce the resistance of material to short-time impact action.

The high levels of plastic deformation of metal matrix (matrix flow around fibers) are also detected in [4] under impact dynamic compression tests at strain rates of 2300 sec^{-1} and 3300 sec^{-1} , that were conducted using a split Hopkinson pressure bar. The average compression strain rate and stress in the specimen have been obtained in [4] based on one-dimensional elastic wave propagation theory and on the records of incident, reflected and transmitted pulse [5].

The present study can be attributed to generalization of the known d'Alembert solution to a wave equation by the method of characteristics for one-dimensional case when the properties of a medium along an infinite axis are piecewise different. At the same time it is necessary to note that though the solution by characteristics is completely general and represented in terms of two functions to cause any plane medium section to be put in motion, the revelation of steady state oscillations is inconvenient, as no in all cases allows to define the eigenfrequencies by a simple method. Alternatively, the solution of a problem on oscillations by the method of a separation of variables (the Fourier method) is very time-consuming in the analysis of stresses, as the representation of this solution in terms of modes, each presenting a standing wave (such as $u = A \sin kz \sin kat$), calls for a great many terms of a series at discontinuous in time transmitting of a pulse at the point of a medium.

BASIC FORMULAE

For one-dimensional (along the spatial coordinate) wave process within two semi-infinite media that contact over the plane $z = 0$ the following equations for displacements $u_i(z, t)$, $i = 1, 2$ hold true:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} = a_i^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

Here $a_i = \sqrt{E_i / \rho_i}$ is acoustic speed that is appropriate to the media $i = 1, 2$ by its elastic module E_i and specific density ρ_i . It is assumed that $-\infty < z < 0$ at $i = 1$ and $0 < z < \infty$ at $i = 2$. Positive time $t > 0$ is measured from the moment when the first wave reaches the contact surface. Let the direct wave moves to the plane $z = 0$ out of the region $z < 0$ from left to right. Displacements of points within the left region in this situation are evaluated by the function of difference between time and spatial coordinates $f(t - z/a_1)$ at $t \leq 0$. From the moment in time at $t = 0$ the direct wave is reflected from the boundary of the right region $z = 0$ and it begins to move counter in the left region $z \leq 0$ as it should be the back wave. Within the right region the direct wave only will travel as transacted through the contact plane into the region of zero initial disturbance. Generally, these displacement waves are dependant on binomial arguments $t \pm z/a$, which are the characteristics of equations (1): for the direct wave a sign “-“ is taken and for the back wave “+”. In accordance with the d'Alembert's formula we shall accept a purely theoretical definition for the wave displacements in the above-mentioned semi-infinite ranges:

$$u_1(z, t) = \theta_1(t - z/a_1) + \theta_2(t + z/a_1), \quad u_2(z, t) = \mathcal{G}(t - z/a_2) \quad (2)$$

The initial functions at $t = 0$ for the wave process within two diverse regions are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(z, 0) = f(-z/a_1), \quad \frac{\partial u_1(z, 0)}{\partial t} = f'(-z/a_1), \quad -\infty < z < 0 \\ u_2(z, 0) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial u_2(z, 0)}{\partial t} = 0, \quad 0 < z < \infty \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

From contact conditions:

$$u_1(0,t) = u_2(0,t), \quad E_1 \frac{\partial u_1(0,t)}{\partial z} = E_2 \frac{\partial u_2(0,t)}{\partial z}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

we have got the relation for the functions entering in second member of equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_1(t) + \theta_2(t) &= \mathcal{G}(t); \\ [\theta_1'(t) - \theta_2'(t)]\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} &= \mathcal{G}(t)\sqrt{E_2\rho_2} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Here $\sqrt{E_i\rho_i}$, $i = 1,2$ is dynamic stiffness or an acoustic impedance designates it.

Notice that equations (5) are written at $z = 0$ to detect a relationship between the functions $\theta_1, \theta_2, \mathcal{G}$, and the final form of the functions for direct waves $\theta_1(t - z/a_1), \mathcal{G}(t - z/a_2)$ and for a back wave $\theta_2(t + z/a_1)$ is derived from the initial conditions (3). In such a manner from (5) can be found:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_2(\zeta) &= \frac{\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} - \sqrt{E_2\rho_2}}{\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} + \sqrt{E_2\rho_2}} \theta_1(\zeta) - C \\ \mathcal{G}(\zeta) &= \frac{2\sqrt{E_1\rho_1}}{\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} + \sqrt{E_2\rho_2}} \theta_1(\zeta) + C \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The constant C should be taken zero at zero displacements of two media as a rigid body. The argument ζ has the meaning not only of time but the characteristic $t + z/a_1$ as well deriving $\theta_2(\zeta)$ from the first relationship in (6) or $t - z/a_2$ deriving $\mathcal{G}(\zeta)$ from the second relationship. The notation itself of the direct wave in the left region can be expressed as $\theta_1(t - z/a_1)$. The argument of function θ_1 alters in the relationship (6) according to the characteristics of functions \mathcal{G}, θ_2 . Specializing the direct wave function to the initial conditions at $t = 0$ given in (3), with allowance for derivation of function \mathcal{G} from (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_1(-z/a_1) &= f(-z/a_1), \quad z < 0 \\ \theta_1(-z/a_2) &= \theta_1'(-z/a_2) = 0, \quad z > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

It follows from (7), that the function $f(z)$ is specified at a positive semi-axis, that is $f(z) = 0$ at $z < 0$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(z,t) &= f\left(t - \frac{z}{a_1}\right) + \frac{\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} - \sqrt{E_2\rho_2}}{\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} + \sqrt{E_2\rho_2}} f\left(t + \frac{z}{a_1}\right), \quad -\infty < z < 0, \quad t > 0 \\ u_2(z,t) &= \frac{2\sqrt{E_1\rho_1}}{\sqrt{E_1\rho_1} + \sqrt{E_2\rho_2}} f\left(t - \frac{z}{a_2}\right), \quad 0 < z < \infty, \quad t > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

At the initial moment $t = 0$ as the front of the direct wave approaches a left boundary $z = 0$ we shall give a specification to the stress as

$$\sigma_0 = E_1 \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial z} \Big|_{t=0, z=0} = -(E_1 / a_1) f'(0) = -\sqrt{E_1 \rho_1} f'(0) \quad (9)$$

A pulse of compression acts on the boundary of media $z = 0$ necessarily at the positive value of a derivative $f'(0)$, then the velocity $v_0 = f'(0)$ is positive. It is quite obvious, that at the moment $t = 0$ the stress and the velocity of a reflected wave (or reflected pulse designated further by a superscript R) and the pulse passing into the second medium (designated by a superscript T) at the boundary will be related to σ_0 and v_0 by the following factors:

$$\sigma_1^R = \sigma_0 (K_2 - K_1) / (K_1 + K_2), \quad \sigma_2^T = 2\sigma_0 K_2 / (K_1 + K_2) \quad (10)$$

$$v_1^R = v_0 (K_1 - K_2) / (K_1 + K_2), \quad v_2^T = 2v_0 K_1 / (K_1 + K_2) \quad (11)$$

where $K_i = \rho_i a_i = \sqrt{E_i \rho_i}$ is the dynamic stiffness of the layer of specific material.

The following inference can be stated by dint of analysis of the factor combination in the expressions for stress and velocity (10), (11). The transmission of a pulse of pressure through the boundary of two media will be either partially blocked at passage into less rigid medium with the increment in velocity of particles v (in this case $\text{sgn } \sigma_1^R = -\text{sgn } \sigma_1^0$, and $|\sigma_2^T| < |\sigma_1^0|$, $v_2^T > v_1^T$), or amplified as a velocity is reduced at passage into more rigid medium (in this case $\text{sgn } \sigma_1^R = \text{sgn } \sigma_1^0$ and $|\sigma_2^T| > |\sigma_1^0|$, $v_2^T < v_1^T$) depending on the ratio of the dynamic rigidities K_1 and K_2 . A stepwise change in physical properties of a medium in the outlined manner has an effect on modification of its dynamic responses - the pulse of pressure I_P and the dynamic pulse I_V :

$$I_P = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \sigma_z dt, \quad I_V = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \rho v^2 dt \quad (12)$$

The reflected pulse is absent when the value K_i is independent of i and in this case the transmitting pulse is equal to the initial one, marked by a zero. In case of reflecting from an absolutely rigid layer ($K_2 = \infty$) corresponding plain result $\sigma_1^R = \sigma_0$, $\sigma_2^T = 2\sigma_0$, $v_1^R = -v_0$, $v_2^T = 0$ follows from (10), (11), and when the contact surface is a free surface that is in the absence of the second medium ($K_2 = 0$) we obtain $\sigma_1^R = -\sigma_0$, $\sigma_2^T = 0$, $v_1^R = v_0$, $v_2^T = 2v_0$. It is precisely the last case that will characterize the wave process spreading up to a back surface - the face plane of a sandwich plate. The pressure pulse is applied on the face surface of the upper layer, see Fig. 1. It being blocked and branched in layers changes its sign in the last lower layer. The estimation of the tensile stresses inevitably appearing due to reflecting from a free surface and converting in all layers is of interest in an effort to predict a slabbing failure.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

First we emphasize, that resulting form of the solution of a wave problem (8) for the layered system with suddenly changing dynamic stiffness of layers together with appropriate initial and boundary conditions completely defines the displacement of points in layers as soon as a function f is found. If the parameters of initial pulse are known from boundary conditions there are the

expressions (10), (11) for a determination of stress and velocity of particles in layers. These formulae are useful having generalized them on a greater number of layer interfaces.

Fig. 1. Typical structure of a sandwich panel exposed to a normal surface impact.

Let us assume that the function $f(z - at)$ allows defining the initial pulse and accordingly the stress σ_0 from initial conditions for a boundary value problem. For example it can be assumed in applied analysis that a short-term impact is delivered by a striker in the form of a plate with identical performance attributes to that of the first panel layer ($K_0 = K_1, h_0 = h_1$) and velocity v_0 , see Fig. 1. Then during the contact of a striker with the first layer at rest the initial velocity of its face surface is $v_1 = v_0 / 2$ and the compression stress equals $\sigma_0 = -K_1 v_1 = -K_1 v_0 / 2$. As time $\Delta t = 2h_0 / a_0 = 2h_1 / a_1$ passes the striker recoils.

Based on relations type of (10), (11) the analysis of stress in a multilayer plate is the most justified at a short-term impact loading, when the time of applied pressure pulse t_* does not exceed double time of a wave travel across the thickness of a separate layer, that is $t_* \leq 2h_i / a_i, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. In this case the reflected wavelet from an opposite surface of the layer will not be superimposed on the pulse transmitting into the layer through the first surface. To facilitate the analysis the monotone variation of dynamic stiffness of the layers was assumed in [6]. In case of a large number of layers n and the dynamic stiffness decrease on an arithmetic progression as the back surface of a stack is approached, the compression stress in the lower layer stemming from the pulse of pressure applied to the upper one is dropped by a factor of $2^{n-1} (n-1)! / [(2n-1)!!]$, i. e. it can be arbitrary small as n increases. The direct pulse is reflected from the lower back surface of a stack and whereupon the tensile stress is found to be the greatest in the upper layer due to amplification of blocking of the transmitting inverse pulse which is up-directed to the upper layer. Therefore the greatest tensile stress is reduced of only 20% as compared to σ_0 . Unlike a homogeneous plate, in which the alternating stresses of compression and tension are equal in magnitude, the greatest tensile stress in the upper layer is reduced by a factor of $2^{2(n-1)} n!(n-1)! / [(2n-1)!!]^2$ at the structure of a stack specified in [6], that is only as large as $\pi n / 4(n-1) \approx 0.25\pi$ at a greater n .

Let us consider the arbitrary structure of a sandwich panel in which the dynamic stiffness of layers equals accordingly $K_i, i = 1, 2, 3$. With application of pulse initiating the stress σ_0 in the first layer the stress pattern in layers and the normal surface stresses varies in time according to the sound speed of longitudinal waves and the layer thickness. Complexity of the process resulting in superposition of the waves reflected and transmitted across the contact surfaces can be somewhat clarified when a monotonic variation of dynamic stiffness is assumed in the stack structure and also when the specific density, modulus of elasticity and layer thickness could be priority chosen to mach the level time interval of a wave travel lengthwise of thickness of every layer that is $h_i / a_i = Const$. When it is considered that a panel back surface is a free surface, the stress in the layer bounded below

by this surface could be of specific interest as with a pulse reflected from a free surface the stress becomes tensile. From (10) the following expression for it can be easily derived

$$\sigma_{1-3}^R = -4\sigma_0\chi_3/(1+\chi_1)(1+\chi_3) \quad (13)$$

where $\chi_1 = K_1/K_2$, $\chi_3 = K_3/K_2$. The stress due to tension pulse having generated by the compression pulse reflection from the back surface and returned to the first layer can be written:

$$\sigma_{1-3-1}^T = -16\sigma_0\chi_1\chi_3/(1+\chi_1)^2(1+\chi_3)^2 \quad (14)$$

This tension stress can be superior to that of the lower layer, if, as it is seen from (13), (14) the relative value of dynamic stiffness of the first layer χ_1 is great enough. Figure 2 *a*, *b* presents the tension stress from an impulse wave resulting after reflection of the compression pulse in the third layer and having returned into the first layer. In the latter case, see Fig. 2 *b*, remarkable for the constant level of stresses, the stacking sequence of a sandwich panel is designed through module of the sum of logarithmic relative stiffness squared.

Fig. 2. Variation of the relative stress (with respect to σ_0) in the third layer $\bar{\sigma}_{1-3}^R$ following a wave reflection from a back surface of a panel (*a*) and further transmitted into the first layer $\bar{\sigma}_{1-3-1}^T$ (*b*) versus relative dynamic stiffness of the panel $\chi_i = \sqrt{E_i\rho_i/E_2\rho_2}$ $i = 1,3$.

In case of symmetric sandwich structure ($\chi_1 = \chi_3 = \chi$, $h_1 = h_3$) an inequality $\sigma_{1-3}^R > \sigma_{1-3-1}^T$ takes place. In the additional clause the simple design expressions can be deduced for the second (middle) layer in view of superposition of the compression and tension waves.

Let us adopt a midlayer thickness h_2 such, that $h_2/a_2 = h_1/a_1$, then the intersection of opposing pulses can happen only at contact surfaces regardless of the fact that $h_1 \neq h_2$. It means that transmitting and reflecting pulses are generated at the contact surfaces when the impulse wave reaches them on both sides at the appropriate points spaced $\Delta t = 2h_i/a_i$ apart along the time-axis, see Fig. 3.

Incident on surface pulses (approaching a contact surface) are transmitted through it with the index of refraction $2/(1+\chi)$ in the first and the third layers, and the reflected pulses in these layers are generated through refractive index $(1-\chi)/(1+\chi)$. The refractive indexes in transmission and reflection will be accordingly $2\chi/(1+\chi)$ and $(\chi-1)/(\chi+1)$ when a pulse approaching the contact surface on the side of a midlayer.

Fig. 3. Scheme of branching of pressure pulses on the contact and face surfaces of a panel at the instants divisible by a wave traveling time along the thickness of one layer. $t_0 = h_i / a_i = \text{Const}$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Fig. 4. Variation of a relative stress $\bar{\sigma}_z = \sigma_z / \sigma_0$ in the midlayer $i = 2$ of a symmetric panel versus a relative dynamic stiffness $\chi = \sqrt{E_1 \rho_1 / E_2 \rho_2}$. Bold curves 1, ..., m are related to time intervals $mt_0 < t < (m+1)t_0$, and the dashed ones correspond to the contact surfaces at $t = mt_0$. See Fig. 3, odd m refers to the left contact surface (a) and even m to the right one (b).

The behavior of pulsating stresses in the midlayer in different time intervals is seen from the curves in Fig. 4. Contact stresses for points $A_i, i = 1, \dots, 6$, shown accordingly in Fig. 3, differ in magnitude from the stresses in the midlayer as the former are generated by the pulses with two-way transmitting and the second ones - by the generated pulse including the reflection in the midlayer. With an increased stiffness of face layers inherent in sandwich panels the stresses in the midlayer are compressive at initial instants of branching pulses, however they become tensile in succeeding moments.

The acoustic analysis carried out in the paper is convenient (because of its sufficient simplicity) for understanding and timely prediction of a generating wave pattern under impact or explosive loading of layered plates.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Variation factors are deduced for the longitudinal wave of displacements, velocities and stresses normally propagating to the layers of a layered medium and transiting a contact surface of two adjacent layers of different dynamic stiffness. These factors are applied to the analytical construction of relationships for branching and superposition of pressure pulses in the layers of a sandwich panel at impact loads.
2. The results suggest that the wide variation spectrum of the transverse normal stress prevail at elastic impact on a front face of either layer. The greatest stress depends on the relative dynamic stiffness of sandwich layers and their relative thickness. It was shown that the tensile stress in the rigid first layer that in the beginning has been exposed to an impact load, on a pulse return can exceed the stress in the third layer in which a tensile pulse was generated by the reflection of a pressure pulse from a back surface. This is not the case for a sandwich of symmetric structure.
3. In case of the symmetric structure of a panel including a soft midlayer the transverse normal stresses within the midlayer not become positive and crucial in spalling fracture till after travelling of the first stress wave, its reflection from a back surface and branching at contact surfaces of the layer. Tensile stresses at these surfaces can exceed the ones within the midlayer.

REFERENCES

1. J. D. Achenbach, "Wave Propagation in Elastic Solids", North-Holland, Amsterdam, (1973).
2. Yu. N. Rabotnov, "Mechanics of Solid Body", Moscow, "Nauka", (1979), p. 744, (in Russian)
3. V. K. Goloubev, S.A. Novikov, and Yu. S. Sobolev, "Effect of Temperature on a Spalling Fracture of Polymers", *J. of Applied Mechanics and Technical Physics*, "Nauka", Siberian Branch, Vol. 131, No 1, pp. 143-150, (1982), (in Russian).
4. Woei-Shyan Lee and Wu-Chung Sue, "Dynamic Impact and Fracture Behavior of Carbon Fiber Reinforced 7075 Aluminum Metal Matrix Composite", *J. of Composite Materials*, Vol. 34, No. 21, pp. 1821–1841, (2000),
5. U. S. Lindholm *J. Mech. Phys. Sci. Solids*, Vol. 12, pp. 317-335, (1964).
6. N. H. Ahmadeev, and R. H. Bolotnova, "Propagation of Stress Waves in Layered Media under Impact Loads", *J. of Applied Mechanics and Technical Physics*, "Nauka", Siberian Branch, Vol. 149, No. 1, pp. 125–133, (1985).